

The Effect Of Using The Strategy (5es) In Developing Historical Thinking Skills For Middle School Students In History

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Abstract

The current research aims to know the effect of using the 5 Es strategy in developing historical thinking skills among middle school students.

To achieve the research goal, the researcher put the following two hypotheses:

1- There are no statistically significant differences at the level (0.05) between the average scores of students of the experimental group and the average of the students of the control group in the scale of historical thinking skills in the post-test.

2- There are no statistically significant differences at the level (0.05) between the average scores of students of the experimental group in the scale of pre and post historical thinking skills.

The researcher followed the experimental design with partial control in design for the research, and the researcher intentionally selected a sample of fifth literary students from Ibn Al-Haytham Secondary School affiliated to the Directorate of Diyala Education for the academic year 2017-2018 for the purpose of applying the experiment, as the number of sample individuals reached (64) students divided into two divisions and by the rate of (31) students in the experimental group and (33) students in the control group, and after excluding the students, the number of students of the experimental group became (30) students and the number of students of the control group (30) students, and the researcher conducted between them the equivalence in the variables (intelligence, time age, achievement For parents, study of historical thinking skills For me).

The researcher analyzed the content of the specific subject, prepared a test that measured historical thinking skills, and used a standardized tool for both groups of research, which is the test of historical thinking skills. The researcher studied the two research groups himself during the trial period, which lasted (15) weeks. And use (T-test) for two independent samples, and (T-test) for two interconnected samples, and a set of statistical means to process the research data. By statistically processing the data, the results showed the superiority of the experimental group over the control group in the test of developing pre and post historical thinking, and in light of the research results, the researcher recommends attention to the use of modern teaching strategies, including the Five Ys strategy (5Es) in teaching European history for the fifth literary grade, and to complement the current study, The researcher suggested several proposals that study the effect of the 5Es strategy on variables and other academic stages.

1. Introduction

The current era is characterized by the rapid scientific development, which requires individuals to possess the foundations of scientific and practical life, through sound scientific thinking that contributes to the development of creativity energies, away from conservation and indoctrination, which prevails in most of our schools, programming minds, and is able to emerge from a culture of receiving information to The culture of building, processing, and converting it into knowledge is the discovery of relationships and phenomena that enable it to move from the stage of knowledge to the stage of knowledge “thinking in thinking”, so interest has increased recently in developing the mental capabilities of individuals, developing thinking and moving away from conservation and Indoctrination and stuffing the minds of the students, to prepare a citizen capable of innovation and to predict the unknown future, which could face the world. (Khader,.2006.p45)

Perhaps the phenomenon of weakness in thinking and relying on memorization and indoctrination is almost one of the most complex problems facing those in charge of teaching, as the teacher is still captive to the traditional methods that emphasize theoretical and formal aspects and on explanation and indoctrination and focus on the transfer of information as in the books set and communicated to students in a way that does not help them to

Developing their thinking skills, as it makes the teacher the focus of the educational process and does not allow the student the opportunity to learn by himself or how to learn. This is due to the lack of traditional methods to meet the needs and requirements of intellectual growth, it is necessary to find strategies and methods that An effective, modern study that increases students' motivation towards the lesson, so the problem of the study is its attempt to identify the effect of using the five 5Es strategy, which may contribute to addressing some aspects of the problem or reduce its severity.

Based on the foregoing, the problem of this research can be formulated with the following question:

Does the 5Es strategy affect the development of historical thinking for literary fifth graders?

Second: The importance of research

With the beginnings of the twentieth century, the world witnessed a great scientific revolution, since science and modern scientific developments and their scientific applications in various areas of daily life have become one of the most important characteristics that characterize human societies in our present time, which we often describe as the era of the Internet, space and nuclear energy, and that All of these scientific and industrial achievements that we feel the effects of in our daily life occurred as a result of the human being reaching the scientific method and applying it in all aspects of life, and through that man was able to achieve this scientific breakthrough during a record period not exceeding several decades, and he was not able to achieve Yeh during the past decades.

(Hussein, 2009:p 452)

Education is the process of directing individual growth in an integrated manner mentally, psychologically, spiritually and socially, preparing it for integration into society and helping it to acquire ethical skills, habits and norms that are in line with the society's philosophy, values and customs, and paper to become a beneficial member in its society(Hariri,p 2012: 62).

As education has evolved in terms of its concept, goals and function, this development must extend to the means that the school is the first of its methods, as well as the curriculum which is the millstones in it because of its importance and a vital center in the educational process that increases and develops with the development of life and its complications, which called the stakeholders By education, to take care of the curriculum in planning, implementation, evaluation and development, as a result of this, the concept of the curriculum develops and speaks in a manner that responds to modern educational changes and trends . (Atiyah, 2008:p 21-22).

The curriculum must be based on an educational thought or educational theory with dimensions that includes the philosophy of the society in which we live, the nature of the learner that we prepare and educate, and the type of knowledge that we want to provide it.

(Hammadat, 2009:p 65).

Modern strategies are the means that helps to transfer the educational content of knowledge, information and skills, and translate it in a way that ensures the student to interact with the academic subject and methodological activities, teachers and students, and to follow the appropriate strategy helps both the teacher and the student to achieve educational goals easily and easily

(Al-Bawi, 2012, p. 8).

The Yaat strategy is one of the five modern strategies that are effective in developing scientific thinking among learners, as it provides an opportunity for them to practice the methods of science, its processes, skills, and investigation themselves, and here the learner behaves in the behavior of the small world in his research and reaches results. (Al-Hailah, 2002: p213).

The first appearance of the five ya strategy consisted of five phases which are (participates, explores, explains, develops, evaluates) called the five ya strategy, which is an educational model based on the constructive approach to education, which sees that learners establish new ideas based on their old ideas and from this basis A five-strategy strategy has emerged that can be used in all ages.

(1994Greene stvavt)and (Kay Treiber 1998) believe that teaching history subject should focus on higher thinking skills, and this requires the interpretation and analysis of information in order to find a solution to a problem that cannot be solved by recounting and retrieving previous information but rather by logical thinking and the proper use of reason (Khreishah, 2004, p. 150).

The aim of the current study is to identify (the effect of using the Five Ys strategy in developing historical thinking skills for middle school Research hypotheses:

Research hypotheses:

1- There are no statistically significant differences at the level (0,05) between the average scores of students of the experimental group and the average scores of students of the control group in the scale of dimensional historical thinking skills.

2- There are no statistically significant differences at the level (0.05) between the average scores of students of the experimental group in the scale of pre and post historical thinking skills.

Research limits: Limitation of Research

The current research is limited to: -

- 1- Literary fifth graders in one of the day preparations for boys in the Department of Pure Education, affiliated to the General Directorate for Diyala Education.
- 2- The first semester of the year 2017-2018.
- 3- The first five chapters of the book (Modern and Contemporary European History) to be taught by the Ministry of Education for the fifth literary grade for the academic year 2017-2018 students).

Defining terms:

First - the effect I knew

- **Amer (2006) states:** "Every negative or positive change affects a project as a result of any development activity" (Amer, ,2006,p87)

Procedural definition of the researcher: -

It is: The amount of change that history history leaves by using the Five Ys strategy in developing critical thinking among literary fifth graders.

Second: the strategy

- **Al Khazaleh, et al., 2011** The group of teaching moves and procedures or the group of teacher movements within the classrooms or the group of teaching procedures previously selected

(Al-Khazayleh, et al, 2011, p. 258).

Procedural definition of the researcher: -

It is a set of procedures and sequential steps that the researcher performs in the classroom while teaching history subject according to the five YA strategy.

Three- The Five Ys 5E, s

Olives and Olives 2003: - It is a strategy that is implemented according to five consecutive steps in which the learner plays a positive role during educational situations through the active interaction between the teacher and the learner depending on the educational activities prepared with the aim of developing scientific concepts and science processes. (Olives and Olives, 2003,p 221)

Procedural definition of the researcher

"A strategy through which (fifth-grade literary students) is taught the subject of modern and contemporary European history and its impact on developing historical thinking skills."

IV- Skills

Mayer, R, (1999)

"The thing that an individual learns and performs with ease and accuracy, whether this performance is physical or mental." (mayer, 1973; p 563)

Procedural definition of the researcher

The ability of students (the research sample) to perform cognitive skills in historical thinking through the strategy of the Five Ys 5E, s).

Fifth: Historical thinking

Khraisheh 2004 "is a mental agent that the history student uses when he deals with texts and historical evidence in a scientific way" (Khraisheh, 2004, p. 128)

Procedural definition of the researcher

"It is the ability of (students of the research sample) to perform the mental skills of history accurately and easily, through the use of a number of historical thinking skills.

Fifth: The preparatory stage

It is a stage that comes after the intermediate stage and includes grades (fourth, fifth, and sixth) with its scientific and literary branches (Ministry of Education, 1977, p. 4).

Chapter II

Theoretical aspects and previous studies

5 E Strategy, E is a constructive learning educational strategy consisting of five procedural steps: Engagemnt, Exploration, Explanation, Explanation, Expansion, Expansion, Calendar, Elaboration, used by the teacher to help students build their knowledge, develop concepts, and how they think.

(Lulu 2011,p 44)

The 5 Ys Strategy Steps 5E, s

1- Engagemnt stage

This phase aimed at motivating learners and raising their curiosity, as the teacher at this stage creates excitement, generates curiosity, raises questions, encourages prediction, and infer responses that reveal information and experiences of learners and how they think about the topic and the role of the learner lies in showing interest on the topic through self-questioning and that learners ask themselves why This happened what can I find out about it (Al-Arrash 2014.p 14)

2- Exploration phase

At this stage, learners have the opportunity to deal directly with phenomena and materials, and when learners deal with these activities, they also have special experience with the phenomenon as well. When learners work in light of work teams, they build a common experience base that helps them in the process of participation and communication and the role of the teacher to provide learners and direct their interest and inquire their feedback that In turn, it directs teaching towards exploration. (Admin, 2010, p155)

3- Explanation phase

The teacher directs the students' thinking so that they build the idea of the topic in a cooperative way by encouraging them to give explanations about the results that they communicated to them with their own words and expressions and helps them to process and mentally organize them after that by providing the appropriate language necessary to reach the idea of the topic.

(The Kurds 2009, 56p)

4- The expansion stage: Elaboration phase

The expansion is centered around the learner and aims to help him mentally organize the experiences he obtained by linking it with a similar precedent as it discovers new applications of what has been learned and the concepts that have been built should be linked to other ideas and experiences to make the learners think about what their current thinking is thought and we should ask them to use The concept language is an added dimension to another, and it is appropriate to help them apply what they have learned by researching the interrelationship between the direction of science and its mastery and society and understanding the history and nature of it. The teacher must give sufficient time to apply what they have learned in new situations and link it to other topics. (Sadiq 2003, p22)

5- The evaluation phase

A continuous diagnostic process that provides the opportunity for the teacher to determine to what extent the learner has understood the topic and uses the evaluation or evaluation during any stage of

The educational process phases: Looking at a calendar as a continuous process makes structuralism a circular system and the learning process itself is open-ended as questions and answers lead to new questions and among the help questions in this regard (Admin, 2010, p158)

Second: - Previous studies

1.Lulu Study, 2011

The study aimed to know (the effect of employing the five-step constructive model in developing the skills of analysis and synthesis in science among students of the ninth grade in Gaza) as the researcher used the experimental curriculum and divided it into two control and experimental groups and used the tool of analysis and installation skills test and the results resulted in the superiority of the students of the experimental group that studied The five-step constructive model for students of the control group who studied in the usual way. (Lulu 2011, p14)

2- Defren 2009 Study

The study aimed to know (the effect of the five registers on the achievement of students and their scientific directions in the cell unit of the sixth grade student), as the study sample included (153) sixth grade students divided into two experimental and control groups as it followed the achievement test to measure the trend and was one of the most important results The study showed that there are differences between the average scores of students in both groups in the achievement test for the experimental group.(Defren 2009 . P12)

Chapter III

The Approach And The procedures of Research:

First: Methods of Research

The researcher relied on the experimental approach because it fits with the nature of the current research, as the experimental approach is one of the safest types of approaches in reaching accurate results(Qandilji, 2008, p. 144)

Second: - experimental design

The researcher adopted an experimental design with partial control, as it is suitable for the conditions of the research

The current design came according to the following shape.

Figure (1)

Post-test	Dependent variable	Pre-test	Independent variable	the group
The dimensional historical development skills	thinking skills Historical	Historical thinking development test	strategy Ys Five	Experimental

test			The usual way	Control
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Third: Research Population:

The current research community was corrupted from all preparatory and secondary schools affiliated to the Diyala Education Directorate, which contain the fifth literary grade of (43) schools.

Fourth: Research Sample:

As the current study requires the selection of one school from among the middle schools affiliated to the Directorate of Diyala Education, the researcher chose pure education and by means of intentional selection a choice

(Ibn al-Haytham Preparatory School for Boys), due to the existence of two divisions for the fifth literary grade in the school, and after the researcher identified the school in which he will apply the experiment, the researcher visited the mentioned school and the researcher randomly chose one of the people and Division A was to represent the experimental group that will study the course of the history of Arab civilization The Islamic strategy of the Five Yates, students reached (31) students, while Division B formed the control group that will study the course of the history of Arab-Islamic civilization in the usual way, and the number of students reached (33) students, and students who failed were statistically excluded in each group When you are sweet For data only, to ensure that their previous experiences do not affect the results of the experiment, and after the exclusion process carried out by the researcher, the number of individuals in the research sample has become (60) students divided into two divisions and by (30) students per section, as shown in

Table (1).

Number of individuals in the sample	The number of students who failed	Number of students	Division	group name	T
30	1	31	a	Experimental	1
30	3	33	B	Control	2
60	4	64	Total		

Fifth: Historical thinking skills

This step consisted of informing the researcher about the European history book for the fifth literary grade, and then defining the scientific material represented in the first five sections, which will be taught during the first semester of the academic year 2017-2018 and after reading and careful reading by the researcher with a view to formulating historical thinking skills and after reviewing Previous studies that dealt with historical thinking skills, the researcher adopted the skills approved by the International Center for History Teaching in the United States of America (NCHS), which consists of five basic skills, namely: 1 - chronology 2- historical comprehension 3 - analysis and interpretation 4 Rue historical research capabilities 5. Analysis of historical issues. Which includes (42) sub-skills, where the researcher presented it to the masters with specialization in the field of history, and teaching methods in order to express their observations about its validity, and thus became finalized after modification and deletion (40) a skill of historical thinking skills.

Sixth: Research Groups Equation:

The researcher was keen, before implementing the experiment, to conduct parity between the members of the two research groups

In some of the variables that may affect the results of the study, they are:

A- The time age is calculated in months.

B- IQ test.

C- The test of developing historical (tribal) thinking skills.

D - the level of parents' achievement.

The data for these variables was obtained directly from the students, and by reference to the school cards

A- The time age calculated in months:

Chronological age measured in months:

The researcher distributed an information form on the research sample that includes information related to the research (the student's name and birth date) and with the approval of the school card, and through the information obtained by the researcher, the ages of the students of the two research groups were calculated and when the arithmetic mean of the experimental group was calculated (191,73), in When the mean of the control group reached (189,97), and using the T-test for two independent samples, as the calculated T value (0,082) was less than the tabular T value of (2,01), and with a degree of freedom (58), This means that there is no

statistically significant difference at the level (0,05), and thus the two groups are equivalent in this variable, so (3) shows that.

Table (3)

Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, calculated and tabulated T value for students' time life

Significance level 0.05	value T		Degree of freedom	standard deviation	SMA	Number of individuals in the sample	the group
	Tabular	Calculated					
Not statistically significant	2,01	0.083	58	10,22	191,73	30	Experimental
				11,13	189,97	30	Control

B- Intelligence Level (Raven) test :

Parity has been performed between students of the two research groups in this variable, using the Raven test for successive matrices, due to its suitability for students. The news consists of (60) items distributed across five groups, which are (A) (B) (C) (D) (E). Gradually, Raven finds that his test measures the ability to think clearly, to consciously observe, and to be able to apply it individually or collectively (as a riff, 2010, p. 190)

The test was corrected with the test key and by giving a score for each paragraph, so the test became (60), so the average score for students in the experimental group reached (31.9), and the average score for students in the control group was (33.1). When using the T-test for two independent samples to know the significance of the statistical differences as in Table (4), it became clear that the difference was not statistically significant at the level (0,05), as the calculated T value (0,55) was smaller than the value Tables (2,07), and with a degree of freedom (58). This indicates that the experimental and control groups are equivalent in the IQ test.

Table(4)

for two research groups (experimental value T calculated and tabulated ,Arithmetic mean, standard deviation .and control) in the IQ test

of A level of Dalal 0.05	value T		Degree of freedom	standar d deviation	SM A	Number of individuals in the sample	the group
	Tabular	Calculated					
Not statistically significant	2,07	0.55	58	8,88	31,9	30	Experimental
				7,14	33,1	30	Control

C- Historical thinking skills test

The researcher applied the test to the individuals of the research sample, and after correcting the test answers, the researcher extracted the arithmetic mean for each group and it became clear that the difference is not statistically significant, as the arithmetic mean of the experimental group reached (18,13), while the arithmetic mean of the control group reached (15.73) Using the T-test for two independent samples, it was found that the calculated T value (1,509) is smaller than the tabular and is (2,01) and at a degree of freedom (58). Thus, the two groups are equivalent in this variable, Table (5) illustrates this.

Table (5)

Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and calculated and tabulated T value for the two research groups (experimental and control) in testing historical (tribal) thinking skills.

Significance level 0.05	value T		Degree of freedom	standar d deviation	SM A	Number of individuals in the sample	the group
	Tabular	Calculated					
Not statistically significant	2,01	1,509	58	5,03	18,13	30	Experimental

Significantly significant				5,29	15,73	30	Control
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Parental level of achievement

1- Level of Fathers Education :: -

Table (6) shows that the experimental and control research groups are statistically equivalent in the fathers level of the father's academic level, as the results of the data using the square of Ca showed that the calculated value of (Ca²) (2,146) is smaller than the tabular value of Ca² (7,81), when Significance level (0,05), with a degree of freedom (3), and after merging the cells (preparatory and institute) into one cell, because the expected frequency was less than (5) and an appendix (10) shows that.

Table (6)
Academic level iterations for parents of two research groups

Significance level 0.05	The value of 2 ka		Degree of freedom	Bachelor and above	Institute	Prep	Medium	Primary	Number of individuals in the sample	the group
	Tabular	Calculated								
Not statistically significant	7,81	2,146	3	5	2	6	6	10	30	Experimental
				7	3	5	9	7	30	Control

The academic level of mothers Level of Mothers Education

Table (7) shows that the experimental and control groups are statistically equivalent in the frequency of the that the calculated value of Ca showed mother's academic level, as the results of the data using the square of of (7) , 81), at the significance level (0,05), and with a value tabular (Ca²) (Ca²) of (0.74) is smaller than the because the expected have been merged (institute, bachelor) degree of freedom (3), and after the cells frequency is less than (5), and an appendix (10) shows that (Table (7))

value Ka calculated	Degree of freedom	Bachelor and above	Institute	Prep	Medium	Primary	Number of individuals in the sample	the group
0.74	3	2	3	5	6	13	30	Experimental
		2	5	5	8	11	30	Control

Seventh: The internal Differences Control:

By setting the variables, it is intended to limit the variables that have an effect on the experiment except the independent variable (Al-Assaf, 1995, p. 308). Where controlling variables is one of the important procedures in experimental research in order to provide an acceptable degree of internal honesty for experimental design. (Melhem, 2005, p. 73).

The following is a presentation of these variables and how to set them:

1- Experimental Extinction

The effect resulting from a number of students leaving the research sample and interrupting it during the experiment, and this leaving or interrupting will have an effect on the results

(Al-Zobaie, 1968, p. 98).

The experiment was not subjected to such conditions.

2- Accident Associated Accidents:

The accompanying accidents are the natural accidents that can occur during the course of the experiment (floods, hurricanes, earthquakes), and abnormal incidents such as (wars, disturbances) that would affect the

course of the experiment, as the experiment did not experience any circumstance or accident that impedes its course .

3- Measurement Tool:

This variable was controlled by using a similar measurement tool with the students of the two research groups, namely the test of historical thinking skills.

4: The Impact of Experimental Procedures

The researcher limited the effect of this factor on the course of the experiment, and this was represented in: -

A- Scientific Article:

The scientific subject was unified for the two research groups, which were represented in the first five chapters of the book Modern and Contemporary European History for the fifth literary grade scheduled for 2017-2018.

B- Teacher: Teacher

The researcher has taught the two research groups himself, to ensure that results are obtained with a high degree of accuracy and objectivity.

C- The trial period:

The duration of the experiment is equal for the two research groups, which is (15) weeks, as it started on 9/10/2017 and ended on 01/30/2018.

D- School building:

The researcher applied the experiment in one school, and in adjacent and similar classes, which is the prep of Jamal Abdel Nasser for boys, and they are similar in their classrooms in terms of the size of the classes, the lighting, the seats, the number of windows, the color of the walls, and other educational methods.

E- Teaching Aids:

The researcher used the same teaching aids while teaching the two research groups, namely (blackboard, white and colored chalk, and the textbook to be taught).

F- Confidentiality of the experiment

It was agreed with the school administration that the researcher is a new teacher of history.

G- Rationing:

The researcher studied three lessons per week for each of the two research groups, according to the method of distributing the shares in the preparatory schools prescribed for the course of the history of Arab Islamic civilization, and according to the weekly lessons schedule prepared by the school administration, it was the distribution of lessons between the two research groups on Sunday, Tuesday and Thursday. The researcher agreed with the school administration to organize the class schedule for the subject of European history for the fifth literary grade as shown in table (8).

(Table 8

Distribution of history lessons among students of the two research groups

The second lesson / 8.50	The first lesson / 8:00 pm	Today
Control group	Experimental group	Sunday
Experimental group	Control group	Tuesday
Control group	Experimental group	Thursday

Eighth The Research Involvement:

1- The Scientific Data:

The scientific subject that will be studied during the application of the experiment has been identified, which are the first five chapters of the book on the history of Arab-Islamic civilization,

Behavioral Objectives:

Therefore, the researcher formulated the behavioral goals (140) behavioral goals were formulated according to the six levels (remembering, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis, evaluation) for classification, and in light of the content of the academic subject for students of the fifth literary grade, and to indicate the validity of the goals and determine or invalidity and amendment It was presented to a group of experts and specialists in the field of curricula, teaching methods, measurement and evaluation.

Teaching Plans:

So the researcher prepared teaching plans for the experimental group according to the five-strategy of the Yates, and prepared plans for the control group according to the usual method, and these plans were presented to a group of experts specialized in the curricula and teaching methods, to explore their views on the suitability of these plans to the content of the subject and their behavioral goals.

2- Preparing the Research Tools:

One of the requirements of this research is to prepare a test to develop historical thinking skills (the research sample) after the end of the experiment to identify the effectiveness of the five Yat strategy in developing historical thinking skills for middle school students and accordingly the researcher prepared the test consisting

of (40), a paragraph of multiple choice type Each paragraph has alternatives. To ensure the validity of the paragraphs and their inclusion in the required levels of knowledge, it was presented to a group of experts and specialists in curricula and teaching methods. A percentage of agreement (80%) was obtained on the validity of the paragraphs.

3- Determine the purpose of the test: The purpose of the test At (8.50) a.m., the pre and post tests were corrected by giving one score for the correct answer, and zero for the wrong answer.

The aim of the test in the research is to measure the amount of development of historical thinking skills included in the first five chapters of the book of the history of Arab Islamic civilization scheduled for 2017-2018.

4- Building test: Building test

The test is one of the most used measurement and evaluation tools used by teachers at all levels of the study, as it is one of the important means that relies on measuring and evaluating students' abilities on the one hand, and on the other hand it is also determined by the extent of achieving educational goals and outcomes.

Check the powers of the paragraphs

1- Test Validity:

The aspects of honesty are among the most important characteristics of educational and psychological tests and measures. The validity of the test relates to the goal for which the test is built, and the decision taken based on its degrees, and therefore access to certain inferences, which is one of the features that must be available in the research tool.

(Al-Dahri, Wahib, 1999, p. 35).

For the purpose of verifying the veracity of the apparent test, the researcher presented the test to a group of experts and specialists in the curricula and teaching methods to judge the validity of the paragraphs, their relevance to the goals and the safety of their formulation. According to their opinions, some alternatives for the paragraphs were modified, so that the test in its final form consisted of (40)

Pilot Test:

To verify the validity of the test, and to know the time it takes to answer the paragraphs of the historical thinking skills test, and to verify the clarity of its paragraphs and its accuracy, the researcher applied the historical thinking test to the exploratory sample, which consisted of (100) students from the fifth literary students in Al-Farabi prep for boys and Al-Waqidi preparatory for boys, Where the test was applied to the polling sample on 10/10/2017. After applying the test, it became clear that the response time takes (45) minutes *, and the researcher found clarity of the accuracy of the test items for the students of the exploratory sample.

Analysis of test paragraphs:

It refers to the process of testing students' responses to the test items, and that process includes knowing how difficult or easy each paragraph is and how it is able to distinguish between the individual differences of the trait to be measured, and in which the effectiveness of the wrong alternatives in the paragraphs, especially in the multiple choice paragraphs, is revealed. ,

Where the researcher, after correcting the answers of the students in the exploratory sample, arranged their degrees in a sequential and descending manner from the highest degree to the lowest degree, then a percentage of that sample and its amount (27%) was chosen, which represented the students who obtained the highest grades in the (higher group) and the proportion (27%) of them Represented the students who obtained the lowest grades from (the lower group) in order to balance between the two groups, and the rate became (27) students in each group, where the total sample total (54) students within the upper and lower groups, then their grades were organized and statistically processed to extract the following: -

- 1- Difficulty coefficient
- 2- Coefficient of Excellence
- 3- Effectiveness of wrong alternatives
- 4- Stability of the test

Final Test of Final Test:

After completing the statistical procedures for the test, it became, in its final form, composed of (40) paragraphs, and thus the test became ready for application.

Experiment Procedures:

The researcher started applying the experiment on Tuesday 9/10/2017. The two groups should search after preparing all the requirements of the experiment, including: -

- 1- Applying the test of historical (tribal) thinking skills on the two research groups on October 11, 2017, after applying the Raven test for the purpose of equivalence.
- 2- Conducting the equivalence process between the two research groups in a number of variables mentioned previously.
- 3- Coordination of the weekly schedule of history classes, by allocating the days of Sunday, Tuesday, and Thursday, by three classes per week for each division, as in schedule (8).
- 4- The researcher finished applying the experiment on Wednesday 30/1/2018.

5- The test of historical thinking skills (dimensional) was applied on Wednesday 30/1/2018, and simultaneously in

Ninth: Statistical Tools:

The researcher used in the research procedures and the analysis of its results the following statistical methods

1- Gutman equation: used to calculate the stability of the test.

2- T-test for two closely related samples.

3- T-Test for two independent samples:

4- Item Difficulty Factor:

5- Effectiveness of Distracters

6- Discrimination Equation:

7-Chi-Square

the fourth chapter

Search Results: Search Results

First: Display the results of the research:

The first hypothesis stated that:

- 1- (There are no statistically significant differences at the level (0,05) between the average scores of the experimental group students and the average score of the control group students in the scale of historical thinking skills in the post-test), so it appeared that the average scores of the experimental group students who studied the five ys strategy reached (27,4) and standard deviation (4,25), and that the mean of students of the control group who studied in the usual way was (20.1) and standard deviation (4,33) and using the T-test for two independent samples (t-test) for the purpose of identifying the significance of the difference between the two mediums. The difference is statistically significant, as the calculated T value (4,343) was greater than the values The tabular T-times of (2,01) at the level of (0.05) and the degree of freedom (58), thus rejecting the first hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis which states: (There are statistically significant differences between the average scores of the experimental group students and the average scores of the control group students On the scale of historical thinking skills in post-test and in the interest of the experimental group). Table (12) illustrates this.

Table No. (12)

Results of the T-test for the experimental and control group scores in the scale of post-historical thinking skills

Significance level 0.05	value T		Degree of freedom	standard deviation	SM A	Number of individuals in the sample	the group
	Tabular	Calculated					
Statistically significant	2,01	4,343	58	4,25	27,4	30	Experimental
				4.33	20,1	30	Control

As for the second hypothesis of the research, it is stated that:

2- (There are no statistically significant differences at the level at (0,05) between the average scores of the experimental group students in the scale of pre and post historical thinking skills) After analyzing the results, it became clear that the average scores of the experimental group students who studied history according to the five ys strategy in The scale of tribal historical thinking skills reached (18,13), while the dimensional reached (27.4), and when using the T-test for two interlinked samples to know the significance of the statistical difference between these two averages, it was found that there is a statistically significant difference in the interest of the post test. Calculated T value of (9,187) at the dala level It has (0.05) and a degree of freedom (29) greater than the tabular T value of (2,045), thus rejecting the second hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis which states:

(There are statistically significant differences between the average scores of the experimental group students in the scale of pre and post historical thinking skills and for the benefit of the post test) Table (13) shows that.

Table (13)
T-test results for the experimental group scores (pre and post) in the scale of historical thinking skills

Significance level 0.05	value T		Degree of freedom	standard deviation	SM A	Number of individuals in the sample	the group Experimental
	Tabular	Calculated					
Statistically significant	2,045	9,187	29	5,03	18,13	30	Tribal
				4,25	27,4		Posti

Second: Interpreting and discussing the results: -

The results showed that the students of the experimental group that studied the course of the history of Arab Islamic civilization by using the five Aliyat strategy surpassed the students of the control group who studied the same subject using the usual method in the post test conducted after the end of the experiment; The results also showed a clear progress for the experimental group students in historical thinking, and the reason for the experimental group's superiority over the control according to the researcher's opinion is due to the following reasons:

- 1- The 5-Y strategy, 5E, increases students' self-confidence through dialogue, discussion and exchange of views in the classroom.
- 2- The teaching method according to the 5 5-ys, s is consistent with modern principles of learning and education such as respecting the student's personality, need and inclinations so that it leads him to participate effectively in the educational process.
- 3- The 5-Y strategy, 5E, s moves students from convergence to active and active participation through its five-strategy strategy.

Chapter V

First: Conclusions: -

There are a set of conclusions, which are: -

- 1- The 5E, s strategy was characterized by its effectiveness in developing historical thinking skills.
- 2- The 5-Y strategy, 5E, s has proven its ability to make students the focus of the educational process and this is in line with modern education visions ..
- 3- The use of the 5-y strategy, 5E, s in developing historical thinking skills lends the lesson to vitality and suspense and contributes to extracting the potentialities of students

Second: Recommendations: -

The recommendations confirmed by the researcher are: -

- 1- The researcher emphasized the strategy of the 5 Ys, 5E, s in teaching history, because of its importance in developing historical thinking.
- 3- The need to include history books in the different academic stages of historical thinking skills because the most important purpose of studying history is to consciously deal with multiple historical events on the basis of understanding, assimilation and historical analysis
- 5- Enriching curricula and textbooks with historical thinking skills.

Third: The proposals: -

In light of the research results, the researcher suggests the following: -:

- 1- Carrying out similar studies on other school stages, and on both sexes.
- 2- It measures the effect of the 5E, s strategy on other variables, such as student attitudes toward history, the development of creative and innovative thinking.
- 3- Experimenting with the effectiveness of 5E, s strategy in developing critical thinking

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